

Stability Of Second Order, Third Order Linear And Non-Linear Differential Systems By Population Model

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Abstract

The Observe of nonlinear equations is limited to diffusion of alternatively particular cases and one must support to different strategies of approximation. In this article, we've got mentioned the stableness of 2nd order, 3rd order linear and non-linear systems by way of function roots. In the case of non-linear system we linearize the nonlinear machine below certain distinct conditions and have a look at the stableness of essential factors of the linearized systems. We have also discussed stability of second and third order linear and non-linear differential equations are studied by characteristic roots by Liapunov's method. Necessary theories had been offered, carried out and illustrated with examples. A self-contained idea for homogeneous linear and non-linear system of 2nd order and 3rd order be built with the aid of the usage of fundamental concept of differential equation. The results show good agreement with the results obtained by both methods mentioned above and graphically by utilizing MATHEMATICA and MATLAB.

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Introduction

Generally, Stability way a situation in which something isn't constantly in all likelihood to move or exchange this is the state or quality of being strong. Differential equations were the maximum vital a part of natural and carried out mathematics. Only the simplest differential equations admit answers given by means of explicit formulation. Many properties of answers of differential equations can be decided without finding their specific form. The graphical solution is the special kind of approximate solution. Here we will observe the graphical method to find the approximate answers of second and third-order linear and nonlinear ordinary differential equations. The mathematical formula of diverse special problems consequences in nonlinear differential equations. In many cases, it is viable to update the sort of nonlinear equation by means of a suitable linear equation which approximates the real nonlinear equation near enough to provide valuable outcomes. Such a "linearization" isn't always continually possible; and when it isn't unique nonlinear equation itself should be taken into consideration. In the literature, several analytical M. Liu and M. Fan (2017) developed stability in distribution of a three-species stochastic cascade predator-prey system with time delays and K. Kishimoto (1982) has obtained the diffusive Lotka-Volterra system with three species can have a stable non-constant equilibrium solution. B. P. Demidovitch (1967) various types are discussed for solving stable non-constant equilibrium solution. N. N. Krasovsk (1963) lectures on Mathematical Theory of Stability and A. M. Liapunov (1950) has discussed the General Problem of Stability of Motion. S. L. Ross (1980) has expanded explained Differential Equations and V. I. Zubov (1964) has described the Methods of Liapunov and their Applications. Stability and persistence of three-species models are explained by B. Rai et al (1987). J. H. Vandermeer et al (1968) have an Experimented Approach with the Relationship between Species Diversity and Stability. L. & CERSARI (1959) have an expanded an asymptotic Behavior and Stability Problems. J.-C et al (2021) are detail interpretation can be found of qualitative Analyses of differential Systems with Time-Varying about the solution of the stability analysis. Moussaoui A. et al (2020) have on some extended Routh-Hurwitz conditions for fractional-order autonomous systems of order $\alpha \in (0, 2)$ and their applications to some population dynamic models. Sarkar et al (2021) has extended stability analysis and results for a nonlinear two-species competition model with size-structure has found by Liu Y & He ZR (2021). In this paper, Stability of Second Order Systems by Liapunov's Method and Stability of Second Order process by Characteristic Roots are presented. The advantage of the proposed method is that a set of linear and non-linear systems differential equation by Liapunov's Method and we also presented this paper a study about Stability of Second Order, third order Linear and Non-linear Differential Systems by Population model.

1.2. Stability of Second Order Systems by Characteristic Roots

Let us consider that

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = P(x, y) \quad \frac{dy}{dt} = Q(x, y) \quad (2.1)$$

Let us consider that $(0, 0)$ is an isolated critical point of the system (2.1). Let C be a path of (2.1); let $x = f(t), y = g(t)$, y be a solution of (2.1) defining C parametrically, Let

$$D(t) = \sqrt{[f(t)]^2 + [g(t)]^2} \quad (2.2)$$

Denote the distance between the critical point $(0, 0)$ and the point $R: [f(t), g(t)]$ on C . The critical point $(0, 0)$ is called stable if for every number $\epsilon > 0$, there exists a number $\delta > 0$ such that the following is true: Every path C for which

$$D(t_0) < \delta \quad \text{some value } t_0 \quad (2.3)$$

$$t \geq t_0, D(t) < \epsilon \quad t_0 \leq t < \infty \quad (2.4)$$

2.1: Types of Stability: There are three types of stability-Stable, Asymptotically stable, Unstable

Let us try to analyze this definition, making use of this figure:

Stable:

The critical point $(0, 0)$ is stated to be stable if, corresponding to every positive number ϵ , according to (2.2), the inequality $D(t_0) < \delta$ for some value t_0 in (2.3) means that the distance between the

Figure-1(Using by MATLAB)

critical point $(0, 0)$ and the point R on the path C must be less than δ at $t = t_0$. This means that at $t = t_0$, R lies within the circle K_δ of radius δ about $(0, 0)$. Likewise the inequality $D(t) < \epsilon$ for $t_0 \leq t < \infty$ in (2.4) means that the distance between $(0, 0)$ and R lies within the circle K_ϵ of radius ϵ about $(0, 0)$. If $(0, 0)$ is stable, then every path C which is inside the circle K_δ of radius δ at $t = t_0$ will remain inside the circle K_ϵ of radius ϵ at $t \geq t_0$. Roughly speaking, if every path C stays as close to $(0, 0)$ as we want it to after it once gets close enough, then $(0, 0)$ is stable.

Asymptotically stable:

The critical point $(0, 0)$ is called asymptotically stable if there exists a number $\delta_0 > 0$ such that if $D(t_0) < \delta_0$ for some value t_0 , then

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} f(t) = 0, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} g(t) = 0.$$

Figure-2(Using by MATLAB)

Unstable:

A critical point be called unstable if it is not stable.

Figure- 3(Using by MATLAB)

2.2: Stability of Second Order Linear Systems We consider the linear system

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = ax + by$$

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = cx + dy \tag{2.2.5}$$

where a, b, c, and d are real constants. where $\begin{vmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{vmatrix} \neq 0$ (2.2.6)

Let, $x = Ae^{\lambda t}$ (2.2.7)

λ must satisfy quadratic equation,

$$\lambda^2 - (a + d)\lambda - (ad - bc) = 0 \tag{2.2.8}$$

is called the characteristic equation of (2.1). Let λ_1, λ_2 be the roots of the characteristic equation (2.2.4). We would expect three possibilities, according as λ_1 and λ_2 are real and distinct, real and equal, or conjugate complex. we must consider the following five cases:

1. λ_1 and λ_2 are real, unequal, and of the same sign.
2. λ_1 and λ_2 are real, unequal, and of opposite sign.
3. λ_1 and λ_2 are real and equal.
4. λ_1 and λ_2 are conjugate complex but not pure imaginary.
5. λ_1 and λ_2 are pure imaginary.

Theorem 2.2.1:

If the roots λ_1 and λ_2 of the characteristic equation (2.2.4) are real, unequal and both negative or positive, then the critical point (0, 0) of the linear system (2.2.5) is asymptotically stable or unstable respectively.

Proof: We first assume that λ_1 and λ_2 are both negative and take $\lambda_1 < \lambda_2 < 0$. Then the general solution of (2.1) may be written as

$$x = C_1 A_1 e^{\lambda_1 t} + C_2 A_2 e^{\lambda_2 t}$$

$$y = C_1 B_1 e^{\lambda_1 t} + C_2 B_2 e^{\lambda_2 t}, \tag{2.2.9}$$

where A_1, B_1, A_2 and B_2 are definite constants and $A_1 B_2 \neq A_2 B_1$, and where C_1 and C_2 are arbitrary constants. Choosing $C_2 = 0$, we obtain the solution

$$x = C_1 A_1 e^{\lambda_1 t}$$

$$y = C_1 B_1 e^{\lambda_1 t}, \quad (2.2.10)$$

Choosing $C_1 = 0$ we obtain the solutions

$$x = C_2 A_2 e^{\lambda_2 t} \quad (2.2.11)$$

$$y = C_2 B_2 e^{\lambda_2 t},$$

For any $C_1 > 0$, the solutions (2.2.9) represent a path consisting of “half” of the line $B_1 x = A_1 y$ of slope $\frac{B_1}{A_1}$. For any $C_1 < 0$, they represent a path consisting of the “other half” of this line. Since $\alpha_1 < 0$, both of these half-line paths approach $(0, 0)$ as $t \rightarrow +\infty$. Also, since $\frac{y}{x} = \frac{B_1}{A_1}$, these two paths enter $(0, 0)$ with slope $\frac{B_1}{A_1}$. Similarly, for any $C_2 > 0$ the solutions (2.2.11) represent a path consisting of “half” of the line $B_2 x = A_2 y$; while, for any $C_2 < 0$, the path so represented consists of the “other half” of this line. These two half-line paths also approach $(0, 0)$ as $t \rightarrow +\infty$ and enter it with slope $\frac{B_2}{A_2}$. If $C_1 \neq 0$ and $C_2 \neq 0$, the general solution (2.2.9) represents non-rectilinear paths. Again, all of these paths approach $(0, 0)$ as $t \rightarrow +\infty$. Further, since

$$\frac{y}{x} = \frac{C_1 B_1 e^{\lambda_1 t} + C_2 B_2 e^{\lambda_2 t}}{C_1 A_1 e^{\lambda_1 t} + C_2 A_2 e^{\lambda_2 t}}$$

$$= \frac{c_1 \frac{B_1}{C_2} e^{(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)t} + B_2}{c_1 \frac{A_1}{C_2} e^{(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)t} + A_2},$$

$$\text{We have, } \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{y}{x} = \frac{B_2}{A_2}$$

And so all of these paths enter $(0, 0)$ with limiting slope $\frac{B_2}{A_2}$.

Thus all the paths enter $(0, 0)$ as $t \rightarrow +\infty$, and all except the two rectilinear ones defined by (2.2.10) enter with slope $\frac{B_2}{A_2}$. According to the definition, the critical point $(0, 0)$ is asymptotically stable. If now λ_1 and λ_2 are both positive and we take $\lambda_1 > \lambda_2 > 0$, we see that the general solution of (2.1.1) is still of the form (2.2.9) and particular solutions of the forms (2.2.10) and (2.2.11) still exist. The situation is the same, except that all the paths approach and enter $(0, 0)$ as $t \rightarrow -\infty$. The critical point $(0, 0)$ is unstable.

Example: Stability of Second Order Linear Systems 2.2.1:

Consider the system

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = x - y, \quad (2.2.1.1)$$

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = 12x - 6y,$$

The origin $(0, 0)$ is clearly a critical point of (2.1).

$$\text{Here } \begin{vmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 12 & -6 \end{vmatrix} = 6 \neq 0.$$

And hence $(0, 0)$ is the only critical point of (2.1).

We consider that solution of the form

$$\begin{aligned} x &= A e^{\lambda t}, \\ y &= B e^{\lambda t}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.1.2)$$

where A and B are definite constants.

Substituting (2.2.1.2) in (2.2.1.1) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} A \lambda e^{\lambda t} &= A e^{\lambda t} - B e^{\lambda t}, \\ B \lambda e^{\lambda t} &= 12 A e^{\lambda t} - 6 B e^{\lambda t}, \end{aligned}$$

and this leads to the algebraic system

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - \lambda)A - B &= 0, \\ 2A - (6 + \lambda)B &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

in the unknown λ . For non-trivial solution we have

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1 - \lambda & -1 \\ 12 & -(6 + \lambda) \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (2.2.1.3)$$

Expanding this we obtain the characteristic equation

$$\lambda^2 + 5\lambda + 6 = 0$$

Solving this we find the roots $\lambda_1 = -2, \lambda_2 = -3$. Since the roots are real, unequal, and of negative sign. Hence the critical point $(0, 0)$ of the linear system (2.1) is asymptotically stable.

Example Stability of Second Order Linear Systems 2.2.2:

Consider the system

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dx}{dt} &= -x - 2y, \\ \frac{dy}{dt} &= 5x + y,\end{aligned}\quad (2.2.2.1)$$

The origin (0, 0) is clearly a critical point of (2.2.2.1).

$$\text{Here } \begin{vmatrix} -1 & -2 \\ 5 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 9 \neq 0.$$

And hence (0, 0) is the only critical point of (2.2.2.1).

We assume a solution of the form

$$\begin{aligned}x &= Ae^{\lambda t}, \\ y &= Be^{\lambda t},\end{aligned}\quad (2.2.2.2)$$

where A and B are definite constants.

Substituting (2.2.2.2) in (2.2.2.1) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}A\lambda e^{\lambda t} &= -Ae^{\lambda t} - 2Be^{\lambda t}, \\ B\lambda e^{\lambda t} &= 5Ae^{\lambda t} + Be^{\lambda t},\end{aligned}$$

and this leads to the algebraic system

$$-(1 + \lambda)A - 2B = 0,$$

$$5A + (1 - \lambda)B = 0,$$

in the unknown λ . For non-trivial solution of this system we have

$$\begin{vmatrix} -(1 + \lambda) & -2 \\ 5 & 1 - \lambda \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (2.2.2.3)$$

Expanding this we obtain the characteristic equation

$$\lambda^2 + 9 = 0$$

Solving this we find the roots $\lambda_1 = 3i, \lambda_2 = -3i$.

Since the roots are pure imaginary, hence we conclude that the critical point (0, 0) of the linear system (2.2.2.1) is stable.

2.3: Stability of Second Order Non-linear Systems.

Illustrative Examples.

Example-2.4.1: We consider the system

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x} &= x + x^2 - 3xy, \\ \dot{y} &= -2x + y + 3y^2\end{aligned}\quad (2.4.1.1)$$

The critical points are given

$$x(1 + x - 3y) = 0, \quad (2.4.1.2)$$

$$-2x + y + 3y^2 = 0,$$

Solving (2) the critical points are (0, 0), $(0, -\frac{1}{3})$, $(1, \frac{2}{3})$, (2, 1).

(i) For (0, 0) the corresponding linear system is

$$\dot{x} = x,$$

$$\dot{y} = -2x + y \quad (2.4.1.3)$$

The characteristic equation of (3) is

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda^2 - 2\lambda + 1 &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow (\lambda - 1)^2 &= 0\end{aligned}$$

$\therefore \lambda = 1, 1$

Here the roots are real, equal and both positive and the system (2.4.1.1) is not such that $a = d \neq 0, b = c = 0$.

Hence the critical point (0, 0) is unstable.

(ii) For $(0, -\frac{1}{3})$ we use

$$x = \xi, y = \eta - \frac{1}{3} \text{ in (1) we obtain}$$

$$\dot{\xi} = 2\xi + \xi^2 - 3\xi$$

$$\dot{\eta} = -2\xi - \eta + 3\eta^2, \quad (2.4.1.4)$$

The characteristic equation of the corresponding linear part of (2.4.1.4) is

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda^2 - \lambda - 2 &= 0 \\ \therefore (\lambda - 2)(\lambda + 1) &= 0 \\ \therefore \lambda &= -1, 2\end{aligned}$$

Here the roots are real, unequal and opposite signs.

Hence the critical point $(0, -\frac{1}{3})$ is unstable.

(iii) For $(1, \frac{2}{3})$ we use

$$x = \xi + 1, y = \eta + \frac{2}{3} \text{ in (2.4.1.1)}$$

and obtain $\dot{\xi} = \xi - 3\eta + \xi^2 - 3\xi\eta$

$$\dot{\eta} = -2\xi + 5\eta + 3\eta^2, \quad (2.4.1.5)$$

The characteristic equation of the corresponding linear part of (2.4.1.5) is

$$\lambda^2 - 6\lambda - 1 = 0$$

$$\therefore \lambda = 3 + \sqrt{10}, 3 - \sqrt{10}$$

Here the roots are real, unequal and opposite signs. Hence the critical point $(1, \frac{2}{3})$ is unstable.

(iv) For (2, 1) we use

$$x = \xi + 2, \quad y = \eta + 1 \quad \text{in (1) and we obtain}$$

$$\dot{\xi} = 2\xi - 6\eta + \eta^2 - 3\xi\eta,$$

$$\dot{\eta} = -2\xi + 7\eta + 3\eta^2, \quad (2.4.1.6)$$

The characteristic equation of the corresponding linear part of (2.4.1.6) is

$$\lambda^2 - 9\lambda + 2 = 0$$

$$\therefore \lambda = \frac{9+\sqrt{73}}{2}, \frac{9-\sqrt{73}}{2}$$

Here the roots are real, unequal and both positive.

Hence (2, 1) is an unstable.

From (2.4.1.6)

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{-2x+y+3y^2}{x(1+x-3y)} = c \quad (\text{say})$$

$$c = 0, \quad \left(1 + \frac{1}{6}\right)^2 = \frac{2}{3} \left(x + \frac{1}{24}\right)$$

$$c \rightarrow \infty, \quad x(1+x-3y) = 0 \Rightarrow x = 0, \quad x-3y+1 = 0.$$

The required figure is shown below:

Figure – 4. (Using by Mathematica)

Figure – 5. (Using by Mathematica)

3.Stability of Third Order Systems by Characteristic Roots.

3.1: Stability of Third Order Linear Systems.

We consider the homogeneous linear system

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = a_1x + b_1y + c_1z,$$

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = a_2x + b_2y + c_2z,$$

$$\frac{dz}{dt} = a_3x + b_3y + c_3z, \quad (1)$$

where the coefficients $a_1, b_1, c_1, a_2, b_2, c_2$ are real constants.

Let us take a solution of the system (1) of the form

$$x = Ae^{\lambda t}, y = Be^{\lambda t}, z = Ce^{\lambda t} \quad (2)$$

where A, B, C and λ are definite constants.

If we substitute (2) into (1) we obtain

$$A\lambda e^{\lambda t} = a_1Ae^{\lambda t} + b_1Be^{\lambda t} + c_1Ce^{\lambda t},$$

$$B = a_2Ae^{\lambda t} + b_2Be^{\lambda t} + c_2Ce^{\lambda t},$$

$$C = c_3Ae^{\lambda t} + b_3Be^{\lambda t} + c_3Ce^{\lambda t},$$

which implies that

$$(a_1 - \lambda)A + b_1B + c_1C = 0,$$

$$a_2A + (b_2 - \lambda)B + c_2C = 0,$$

$$a_3A + b_3B + (c_3 - \lambda)C = 0, \quad (3)$$

This system obviously has the trivial solution $A=B=C=0$. But this would only lead to the trivial solution $x=0, y=0$ and $z=0$ of the system. A necessary and sufficient condition that this system have a nontrivial solution is that the determinant

$$\begin{vmatrix} a_1 - \lambda & b_1 & c_1 \\ a_2 & b_2 - \lambda & c_2 \\ a_3 & b_3 & c_3 - \lambda \end{vmatrix} = 0. \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or } (a_1 - \lambda)\{(b_2 - \lambda)(c_3 - \lambda) - b_3c_2\} - b_1\{a_2(c_3 - \lambda) - c_2a_3\} + c_1\{a_2b_3 - a_3(b_2 - \lambda)\} = 0$$

$$\text{or } (a_1 - \lambda)\{b_2c_3 - b_2\lambda - c_3\lambda + \lambda^2 - b_3c_2 - b_1(a_2c_3 - \lambda a_2 - a_3c_2) + c_1(a_2b_3 - a_3b_2 + a_3\lambda)\} = 0,$$

$$\text{or } \lambda - (a_1 + b_2 + c_3)^2 + (a_1b_2 + a_1c_3 + b_2c_3 - b_3c_2 - a_2b_1 - a_3c_1)\lambda - (a_1b_3c_2 - a_1b_2c_3 + a_2b_1c_3 - b_1c_2a_3 - a_2b_3c_1 + a_2b_2c_1) = 0 \quad (5)$$

in the unknown λ . This equation is called the characteristic equation associated with the system (1). Its roots λ_1, λ_2 and λ_3 are called the characteristic roots of the given system. Five cases must be considered:

1. The roots λ_1, λ_2 and λ_3 are real and distinct/different.
2. The roots λ_1, λ_2 and λ_3 are real and any two roots of them are equal and other is distinct.
3. The roots λ_1, λ_2 and λ_3 are real and equal.
4. The roots λ_1 is real and λ_2 and λ_3 are conjugate complex.
5. The roots λ_1 is real and λ_2 and λ_3 are purely imaginary.

Case- 1

The Roots of the Characteristic Equation (5) are Real and Distinct.

If the roots λ_1, λ_2 and λ_3 of the characteristic equation (5) are real and distinct, it appears that we should expect three distinct solutions of the form (2), one corresponding to each of the three distinct roots. This is indeed the case. Furthermore, three distinct solutions are linearly independent. We summarize this case in the following theorem.

Theorem-3.1.1:

Hypothesis. The roots λ_1, λ_2 and λ_3 of the characteristic equation (4) associated with the system (1) are real and distinct. Assume that all the characteristic roots are negative. **Conclusion.** The critical point (0, 0, 0) of the linear system (1) is asymptotically stable. The system (1) has three nontrivial linearly independent solution of the form.

$$x = A_1e^{\lambda_1 t}, A_2e^{\lambda_2 t}, A_3e^{\lambda_3 t},$$

$$y = B_1e^{\lambda_1 t}, B_2e^{\lambda_2 t}, B_3e^{\lambda_3 t}$$

$$z = C_1e^{\lambda_1 t}, C_2e^{\lambda_2 t}, C_3e^{\lambda_3 t},$$

where $A_1, B_1, C_1, A_2, B_2, C_2, A_3, B_3, C_3$ and C_3 are definite constants. The general solution of the system (1) may thus be written as

$$x = C_1A_1e^{\lambda_1 t} + C_2A_2e^{\lambda_2 t} + C_3A_3e^{\lambda_3 t},$$

$$y = C_1B_1e^{\lambda_1 t} + C_2B_2e^{\lambda_2 t} + C_3B_3e^{\lambda_3 t},$$

$$z = C_1C_1e^{\lambda_1 t} + C_2C_2e^{\lambda_2 t} + C_3C_3e^{\lambda_3 t},$$

where C_1, C_2 and C_3 are arbitrary constants

Example-3.1.1: Consider the linear system

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = 7x - y + 6z,$$

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = -10x + 4y - 12z, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dz}{dt} = -2x + y - z$$

We assume a solution of the form

$$x = Ae^{\lambda t}, y = Be^{\lambda t}, z = Ce^{\lambda t} \quad (2)$$

where A, B, C and λ are definite constants.

Substituting (2) into (1), we get

$$\begin{aligned} Ae^{\lambda t} &= 7Ae^{\lambda t} - Be^{\lambda t} + 6Ce^{\lambda t}, \\ Be^{\lambda t} &= -10Ae^{\lambda t} + 4Be^{\lambda t} - 12Ce^{\lambda t}, \\ Ce^{\lambda t} &= -2Ae^{\lambda t} + Be^{\lambda t} - Ce^{\lambda t} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

And this leads at once to the algebraic system

$$\begin{aligned} (7-\lambda)A - B + 6C &= 0, \\ -10A + (4-\lambda)B - 12C &= 0, \\ -2A + B - (1+\lambda)C &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

For non-trivial solutions of this system we have

$$\begin{vmatrix} 7-\lambda & -1 & 6 \\ -10 & 4-\lambda & -12 \\ -2 & 1 & -(1+\lambda) \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

Expanding this, we obtain the characteristic equation

$$\lambda^3 - 10\lambda^2 + 31\lambda - 30 = 0$$

Solving this, we find the roots

$$\lambda_1 = 2, \lambda_2 = 3, \lambda_3 = 5$$

Setting $\lambda = \lambda_1 = 2$ in (4) we get

$$\begin{aligned} 5A - B + 6C &= 0, \\ -10A + 2B - 12C &= 0, \\ -2A + 2B - 3C &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

A simple non-trivial solution of this system is obviously $A = 1, B = C = -1$. With these values of A, B, C and λ , we find the non-trivial solution

$$\begin{aligned} x &= e^{2t}, \\ y &= -e^{2t}, \quad z = -e^{2t}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Now setting $\lambda = \lambda_2 = 3$ in (4), we get

$$\begin{aligned} 4A - B + 6C &= 0, \\ -10A + B - 12C &= 0, \\ -2A + B - 4C &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

A simple non-trivial solution of this system is $A = 1, B = -2, C = -1$.

Using these values of A, B, C and λ , we find the non-trivial solution

$$\begin{aligned} x &= e^{3t}, \\ y &= -2e^{3t}, \\ z &= -e^{3t}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Again setting $\lambda = \lambda_3 = 5$ in (4), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} 2A - B + 6C &= 0, \\ -10A - B - 12C &= 0, \\ -2A + B - 6C &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

A simple non-trivial solution of this system is $A = 3, B = -6, C = -2$.

Using these values of A, B, C and λ , we find the non-trivial solution

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 3e^{5t}, \\ y &= -6e^{5t}, \\ z &= -2e^{5t}, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

By theorem, the solutions (5), (6), (7) are linearly independent and the general solution of the system (1) may be written as

$$\begin{aligned} x &= C_1 e^{2t} + C_2 e^{3t} + 3C_3 e^{5t}, \\ y &= -C_1 e^{2t} - 2C_2 e^{3t} - 6C_3 e^{5t}, \\ z &= -C_1 e^{2t} - C_2 e^{3t} - 2C_3 e^{5t}, \end{aligned}$$

where C_1, C_2, C_3 are arbitrary constants.

Case-2

The roots of the characteristic equation (5) are one distinct and two equal:

If the roots λ_1 of the characteristic equation is real and distinct, it appear that we should expect one distinct solution of the form

$$x = A_1 e^{\lambda_1 t},$$

$$y = B_1 e^{\lambda_1 t},$$

$$z = C_1 e^{\lambda_1 t}$$

Further-more this solution are linearly independent. And the roots λ_2 and λ_3 of the characteristic equation (5) are real and equal, it would appear that, we could find only one solution of the form (2). Except in the subcase $a_1 = b_2 = c_3 \neq 0$, $a_3 = b_3 = c_1 = 0$. This would lead us to expect a second and third solution of the form

$$x = A e^{\lambda t},$$

$$y = B e^{\lambda t},$$

$$z = C e^{\lambda t},$$

$$\text{And } x = (A_2 t + A_3) e^{\lambda t},$$

$$y = (B_2 t + B_3) e^{\lambda t},$$

$$z = (C_2 t + C_3) e^{\lambda t},$$

We can summarize this by the following theorem

Conclusion.

In this article we have discussed about Stability of Second Order Linear and Non-linear Differential Systems by Population model. Stability of second and third order linear and non-linear differential equations are studied by characteristic roots. Stability of second order system is also discussed by Liapunov's method. The Liapunov's method is straight forward and very important for real world situations. We discussed these methods with hypothesis, conclusion and illustrative examples.

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